

TOOL FOR MODELLING OF ALTERNATIVE MITIGATION INTERVENTIONS

Deliverable 3.7

TOOL FOR MODELLING OF ALTERNATIVE MITIGATION INTERVENTIONS

HIGH HORIZONS – D3.7

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Investigators

The tool development within the HIGH Horizons project is led by a team of investigators from CeSHHAR (Zimbabwe) and Wits RHI (South Africa), supported by Burnet Institute (Australia). The core project team brings a wealth of experience and expertise in climate and health research, mathematical modelling, data science, and management to this project.

In Zimbabwe, the Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research team consists of Stanley Luchters (MBBCh, MSc, PhD), Professor and Executive Director; Fortunate Machingura (PhD), the Climate & Health Director; Nelson Muparamoto (PhD), the Climate & Health Research Manager; and Jetina Tsvaki (MSc), Climate & Health Data Scientist and Management Officer. In South Africa, the Wits RHI team consists of Matthew Chersich (MBBCh, MSc, PhD), Research Professor; and Craig Parker (MSc), Data Scientist. The team in Australia is led by Nick Scott (PhD), Associate Professor; and Farah Houdroge (PhD), a mathematical modeller and researcher.

Partners in the project

Partners developing the tool:

1. *Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (CeSHHAR), Zimbabwe* - specialises in maternal, neonatal, and child health research, community-based intervention research, and anthropology.
2. *Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa* - provides expertise in climate change and health, statistics, maternal health, anthropology, and intervention co-creation.
3. *Burnet Institute, Australia* - has expertise in infectious diseases, especially HIV, hepatitis viruses, influenza, and malaria, and in understanding the immune responses to these infections, as well as in climate and health research, mathematical modelling, and data science.

Definitions

Term	Definition
Anaesthetic gases	Gases used in medical procedures to induce anaesthesia, which can be potent greenhouse gases
Atomica	Atomica is a software platform developed by the Burnet Institute that enables the creation of detailed mathematical models of infectious disease transmission, intervention impact, and health system responses
Adaptive Stochastic Descent (ASD)	An optimisation algorithm that replicates the essential aspects of manual parameter fitting in an automated way
Carbon footprint	The total amount of greenhouse gas emissions produced by an organisation or facility
CARBOMICA	An acronym given to a tool developed to assist in strategic allocation of resources to reduce carbon emissions in healthcare facilities standing for CARBOn Mitigation Intervention in HealthCare fAcilities
CO ₂ equivalent	A metric measurement used to compare emissions from various greenhouse gases to an equivalent of carbon
Emissions	The release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Emissions can be direct, such as from burning fossil fuels, or indirect, such as from the production of electricity used to power a building or process. Emissions are typically measured in tons of CO ₂ equivalent (tCO ₂ e)
Emissions scopes	The different categories of emissions that are accounted for in a carbon footprint assessment
Greenhouse gas emissions	Gases that trap heat in the atmosphere and contribute to global warming, including carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide
Greenhouse gases (GHGs)	Any of the gases that contribute to the greenhouse effect, including carbon dioxide (CO ₂), methane (CH ₄), nitrous oxide (N ₂ O), fluorinated gases, and others
Mitigation interventions	Actions taken to reduce or offset the carbon emissions of a facility or organisation
Optimisation modelling	The process of using mathematical models to find the most efficient solution to a problem
Predictive modelling	Using data and statistical methods to make predictions about future events or outcomes
Refrigerant gases	Gases used in refrigeration and air conditioning systems, which can contribute to emissions through leaks or improper disposal

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Executive Summary

The escalating climate crisis poses profound threats to global public health, with extreme weather and deteriorating air quality endangering human wellbeing [1][2]. Despite its mission to protect health, the healthcare sector contributes a significant share of global greenhouse gas emissions (4-5% and up to 8% in some settings), making it comparable to the fifth-largest national emitter globally [3]. The coexistence of health and climate change issues presents a pressing challenge, particularly for disadvantaged communities that confront amplified environmental health risks while struggling with limited financial resources for effective mitigation measures.

Therefore, policy interventions and increased funding are necessary to address health and climate change in a concerted manner. A crucial component of this endeavour involves the development and implementation of a resource allocation tool tailored explicitly for carbon mitigation work within healthcare facilities. This tool can facilitate optimised resource allocation, thereby promoting equitable outcomes and effectively addressing the intertwined concerns of health and climate change.

In response, the CARBOMICA (CARBOn Mitigation Intervention for healthCare fAcilities) tool was created as a resource allocation tool to improve the healthcare sector's carbon management efficacy under the HIGH Horizons project. It informs and guides decision-makers in the strategic distribution of scarce carbon mitigation resources.

The [HIGH Horizons project](#) is a health research and implementation project that aims to fill critical knowledge gaps in quantifying and monitoring heat-related effects on maternal, newborn, and child health (MNCH). It involves eleven partners from ten countries, including the EU, the UK, and Sub-Saharan Africa. One particular focus of the project is the lack of adaptation and mitigation measures in healthcare facilities, which has a negative impact on occupational health among

healthcare workers and carbon emissions. The project also recognises the need for a cost-effective integrated approach that combines adaptation and mitigation initiatives within health facilities, prioritising the wellbeing of healthcare workers and those they serve, and carbon reduction.

The CARBOMICA tool was developed using a comprehensive methodology involving a systematic and collaborative approach incorporating various data science techniques and methods. The development team conducted a needs assessment, collected relevant data, and utilised the Atomica framework (a powerful Python-based tool for modelling complex systems) to analyse greenhouse gas emissions in the healthcare sector. Additionally, Adaptive Stochastic Descent (ASD) optimisation techniques were integrated into the tool to enhance its ability to identify optimal mitigation strategies and resource allocations to maximise carbon reduction.

The CARBOMICA tool involves a decision matrix that evaluates three essential factors: impact, feasibility, and scalability. “Impact” measures the potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions through a particular intervention. “Feasibility” examines how practical and viable it is to implement that intervention. Lastly, “Scalability” assesses whether the intervention can be expanded or replicated on a larger scale.

The tool also provides information on the impact of adopting mitigation interventions under different budget and coverage scenarios within healthcare facilities. These comparative scenarios help us to understand the trade-offs between budget and coverage and the effectiveness of interventions under various constrained circumstances.

CARBOMICA outputs include tables, visualisations for effective communication, user support, and guidance. By offering these features, CARBOMICA enables healthcare facility managers and policymakers to make informed, data-driven decisions for reducing carbon emissions in healthcare settings. Utilising the

decision matrix, stakeholders can prioritise interventions based on their impact, feasibility, and scalability. This is particularly useful for identifying optimal strategies aligning with the facility's carbon footprint goals and financial constraints.

CARBOMICA is a powerful tool that enables the calculation of potential emission reductions for different sources by implementing specific interventions. For example, considering an intervention in Mt. Darwin with a budget constraint of US\$1000, CARBOMICA can estimate the potential emissions reduction of 4% by utilising low Global Warming Potential (GPW) anaesthetic gas, 1% through the use of water-efficient fixtures and appliances, 1% by implementing a solar system, and 1% through carpooling and riding.

Moreover, CARBOMICA allows for optimising carbon reduction based on different budget allocations. For instance, CARBOMICA can determine a carbon reduction of 20% with a budget allocation of US\$20,000, 44% reduction with a budget allocation of US\$50,000 and an impressive 68% reduction with a budget allocation of US\$100,000 providing the corresponding quantities for each intervention to achieve these reduction targets.

CARBOMICA can be utilised by facility managers, sustainability managers, energy managers, and environmental consultants involved in carbon mitigation efforts within healthcare facilities. It is designed to help them assess emissions, identify interventions, and develop targeted strategies for carbon reduction, ultimately supporting cost savings, environmental responsibility, and regulatory compliance. Notably, the tool can also be used by other stakeholders interested in carbon mitigation, such as sustainability committees, finance departments, and regulatory bodies. The flexibility and user-friendly nature of CARBOMICA make it accessible to a diverse range of individuals and organisations involved in carbon reduction efforts.

In summary, CARBOMICA is a versatile tool that facilitates assessing and maximising emission reductions by analysing various interventions and budget allocations. Thus, CARBOMICA is invaluable for developing targeted mitigation initiatives, helping healthcare leaders navigate the complexities of balancing environmental responsibility with operational needs.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The healthcare sector's contribution to greenhouse gas emissions is a significant concern, resulting from various operational activities such as energy consumption, waste generation, and transportation [4-6]. Recognising the need for innovative carbon-cutting solutions, stakeholders in the HIGH Horizons consortium embarked on a mission to address this issue.

CARBOMICA was created to assess the impact of carbon-cutting interventions, identify feasible strategies, and allocate resources effectively. It provides a structured decision-making framework that bridges the gap between sustainability goals and practical implementation. The tool aims to help healthcare stakeholders combat climate change by providing data-driven analysis, modelling, optimisation, and decision support.

CARBOMICA used a stakeholder-driven approach throughout the development process to ensure its relevance and effectiveness [7]. CARBOMICA's functionalities, data inputs, and decision-making frameworks were all shaped by active engagement and stakeholder collaboration. This approach ensured the tool was tailored to the healthcare sector's specific needs and challenges in addressing climate change [7].

CARBOMICA was created in response to the growing emphasis on sustainability and carbon reduction in healthcare operations [8] in the Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs). The tool supports healthcare stakeholders in achieving carbon mitigation goals and promoting sustainable practises within the sector by providing a tailored tool that combines data analysis, modelling, optimisation, and decision support.

1.2 Motivation

The motivation behind developing CARBOMICA was driven by several key factors and concerns related to the healthcare sector's impact on climate change, as supported by the following sources:

1. Environmental Impact:

The healthcare sector substantially contributes to greenhouse gas emissions due to various factors. These include energy-intensive operations, waste generation, and reliance on equipment and transportation powered by fossil fuels [5]. Specifically, emissions arise from hospital care, physician and clinical services, and pharmaceuticals [4]. In particular, buildings in the hospital sector often operate 24 hours per day 365 days per year. Therefore, potential reductions in emissions will be relatively higher in healthcare than in other sectors. These factors collectively contribute to the sector's significant carbon footprint. Addressing these emissions and mitigating their impact on climate change became a growing need within the industry [9].

2. Health Implications:

Climate change has significantly impacted human health, with increased heat-related mortality and morbidity. Every year, over 350,000 people die from extreme heat from various causes, such as cardiorespiratory and metabolic diseases, suicides, and injuries [10]. Furthermore, severe health consequences go beyond deaths, especially in maternal and child health, occupational settings, and indirect consequences [11]. The vulnerability to these effects varies by region and population. [1, 12] call for immediate action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and implement effective adaptations to mitigate the growing health risks associated with climate change.

3. Regulatory Pressures:

Governments and regulatory bodies worldwide have been implementing policies and regulations to curb carbon emissions across various industries, including healthcare, in response to the growing urgency of climate change [13]. Healthcare organisations have faced increasing pressure to comply with these regulations and demonstrate their commitment to sustainability [14].

4. Cost Savings:

Implementing carbon-curbing interventions in healthcare organisations can save costs [15]. Energy-efficient practices, waste reduction measures, and optimised resource allocation contribute to reducing carbon emissions and lead to financial benefits such as reduced energy costs and improved operational efficiency [16].

Considering these factors, the development of CARBOMICA aimed to provide a comprehensive tool that would allow healthcare stakeholders to assess, prioritise, and implement carbon-cutting interventions effectively.

1.3 Objectives

1. Development of a Context-Specific Solution for LMICs:

We aim to design CARBOMICA as a specialised tool for the healthcare sector in LMICs, addressing the distinct needs and challenges these regions face in carbon mitigation.

2. Supporting Evidence-Based Decision-Making in LMICs:

Our goal is to provide healthcare stakeholders in LMICs with a tool that helps make informed decisions. This tool will allow for assessing and prioritising carbon-reduction initiatives based on their real-world impact, feasibility, and potential for scalability in these regions.

3. Enabling Scenario Analysis Relevant to LMICs:

We strive to equip CARBOMICA with features that allow users to develop and analyse scenarios that reflect the unique conditions of LMICs, helping them understand potential outcomes of different carbon-reduction strategies.

4. Resource Allocation Optimised for LMIC Conditions:

With CARBOMICA, we aim to offer optimised solutions for resource allocation, keeping in mind the specific resource constraints and challenges that LMICs often encounter.

5. Promoting Collaboration among LMIC Stakeholders:

We hope to make CARBOMICA a platform for collaboration among healthcare professionals, researchers, and policymakers in LMICs, ensuring the tool aligns well with the specific needs and priorities of these regions.

1.4 Scope

CARBOMICA is a tool designed for the healthcare industry to reduce carbon emissions. It focuses on evaluating and prioritising interventions and strategies, utilising data-driven analysis, providing decision support and reporting, and emphasising stakeholder engagement.

Key features are illustrated in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Key Features and Aspects of the CARBOMICA Tool for Healthcare Carbon Mitigation

2 Methodology

2.1 Conceptual framework

Climate change, with its intricate and diverse facets, necessitates a methodical approach to problem-solving. Within the domain of carbon mitigation measures, there is a noticeable scarcity of accessible data on the effective distribution of monetary resources for high-impact interventions, especially in the African context. In the development of the CARBOMICA tool, a systematic framework was employed to structure and align relevant ideas and concepts. Herein, we present a brief exposition of the foundational framework underpinning the creation of CARBOMICA.

Figure 2: Overall Conceptual Framework

The CARBOMICA tool was developed using a conceptual framework that involved several steps. The first step was to identify the problem, which was the lack of streamlined tools and methodologies to efficiently allocate financial resources towards the most impactful carbon mitigation interventions. The next step was to identify subproblems related to the mitigation interventions and collect data on intervention costs and effectiveness. This involved evaluating the different types of carbon mitigation interventions and their costs and effectiveness.

Once the subproblems were identified, a decision matrix and prioritisation criteria were developed for evaluating the interventions. The CARBOMICA tool used various approaches such as Atomica approach, decision matrix, and ASD optimisation to identify the most effective mitigation interventions. Flowcharts were used to determine the most effective interventions based on the criteria developed in the previous step. The identified interventions were then implemented by allocating financial resources towards the most effective interventions. It was important to ensure that the assumptions made in the

process were satisfied, which involved ensuring that the data used to evaluate the effectiveness and costs of each intervention was accurate and up to date. Finally, the effectiveness of the implemented interventions was evaluated using performance metrics.

2.2 Approach

The approach to developing a resource allocation tool for carbon mitigation in healthcare facilities encompasses key elements such as stakeholder engagement, data collection and management, integration with the Atomica framework, and the development of a decision matrix. By engaging with stakeholders, collecting comprehensive data, utilising the Atomica framework, and employing a decision matrix, the tool aims to address the unique challenges and requirements of carbon mitigation in the healthcare sector. Table 1 below provides an overview of the approach, highlighting its focus on stakeholder involvement, data analysis, scenario modelling, and decision-making processes to effectively allocate resources and prioritise carbon-curbing interventions in healthcare facilities.

Table 1: Strategies and Methods for Carbon Mitigation in the Healthcare Sector

Approach	Description
Stakeholder engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging with stakeholders within the HIGH Horizons consortium, the Burnet Institute and healthcare professionals to understand challenges and requirements specific to carbon mitigation in the healthcare sector. Engaging stakeholders throughout the development process to gather input, expertise, and feedback, ensuring the tool's relevance, effectiveness, and alignment with the healthcare sector's needs.
Data Collection and Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive collection, quality assurance, and organisation of carbon mitigations interventions and carbon emissions, including operations, energy consumption, waste management, transportation, and other factors.
Atomica Framework Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilising the Atomica framework for data analysis and scenario modelling, enabling the modelling of healthcare-specific factors and interactions related to carbon emissions.

Approach	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating optimisation techniques to optimise resource allocations and determine cost-effective strategies for carbon reduction in the healthcare sector. Generating reports and visualisations presenting summarised information, charts, graphs, and other visual representations to effectively communicate scenario analysis results and decision-making processes.
Decision Matrix Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing a decision matrix to evaluate and prioritise carbon-curbing interventions based on impact, feasibility, and scalability, quantifying, and weighing these factors through data analysis and stakeholder consultations.

The development of CARBOMICA, a data science tool, involved a systematic and collaborative approach that incorporated various data science techniques and methodologies.

❖ Stakeholder engagement methods

CARBOMICA employed stakeholder engagement methods throughout the tool's development and implementation. These included several meetings and collaborative sessions to gather input, validate models, and incorporate domain expertise.

❖ Data collection & preprocessing

• Data types & sources

The data collection process began by identifying relevant data needed and with their respective data sources.

The minimum required data included the following.

Figure 3: Data Components for Healthcare Facility Carbon Management and Mitigation Analysis

• Data Preprocessing & Validation

For the CARBOMICA tool, maintaining data quality and reliability is paramount. This is achieved through a multi-pronged approach of preprocessing and validation before integrating data from different sources. The initial phase involves data cleaning, where missing emissions values are methodically filled through techniques like mean or median imputation, while any outliers in emission figures are rigorously inspected using methods like IQR or Z-score for their legitimacy.

To ensure consistency and compatibility, the data undergoes transformation and integration. This encompasses the standardisation of units across all data sets, aligning data to a consistent time frame, and appropriately tagging each entry with its origin for traceability. Further validation steps, like consistency checks and cross-referencing data points across sources, ensure that the integrated data remains trustworthy and devoid of discrepancies.

Finally, maintaining the data's credibility does not end post-integration. Regular reviews, coupled with the invaluable insights from domain experts familiar with carbon emissions, are continually employed. This rigorous process safeguards the data's accuracy and its contextual relevance, reinforcing CARBOMICA's commitment to trustworthy data-driven insights.

- **Data Security & Privacy**

The development and expansion of the CARBOMICA tool have been and continue to be underpinned by rigorous data security measures. In line with the HIGH Horizon Consortium's data protection standards, and given the absence of sensitive patient data, the tool prioritises security at every step. Primarily, the data is securely housed within a closed GitHub repository, ensuring access is limited strictly to the development team.

In terms of the technical infrastructure, a multi-layered approach has been embraced. Encryption standards are paramount, with data encrypted at rest (even within storage devices or platforms like Excel) and during transfer activities, leveraging protocols like SSL or TLS. Additionally, the tool's repository on GitHub is private, bolstered with an additional security layer through Two-Factor Authentication (2FA) for all authorised collaborators.

Regular encrypted backups are taken to ensure data integrity, and the inbuilt version control capabilities of GitHub allow for a transparent audit trail of any modifications to the data or the Python scripts. The tool also advocates for data minimisation, ensuring only essential data components are stored. Transfers outside the primary environment, such as local machine downloads, are safeguarded with secure, encrypted protocols. Lastly, as the tool evolves, regular security audits will be an ongoing commitment, aiming to pre-emptively identify and address any vulnerabilities or security concerns. As CARBOMICA grows, its commitment to maintaining these robust security practices remains unwavering.

❖ Atomica framework

The Atomica modelling and analysis framework is designed to simulate complex systems and support decision-making processes. The framework incorporates various mathematical techniques and algorithms to simulate the dynamics of these systems. Below is how it works.

Figure 4: Workflow for Data Input and Scenario Analysis Using Atomica Engine

❖ Decision matrix

The decision matrix was created to prioritise mitigation interventions in the healthcare sector based on their impact, feasibility, and scalability. Interventions were evaluated and scored for each criterion, considering emission reduction potential, ease of implementation, and potential for expansion. Weighted scores were calculated for each intervention, and higher scores indicated higher priority using the formula below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Priority Score (PS)} &= 0.5 * \text{Intervention Impact Score (IS)} + 0.3 * \text{Feasibility Score (FS)} + 0.2 \\ & * \text{Scalability Score (SS)} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$TS = IS + FS + SS$$

The decision matrix offers a systematic approach for decision-makers to identify and prioritise interventions that can effectively reduce greenhouse gas emissions in healthcare. Below is the matrix used in selecting interventions.

Table 2: Decision Matrix

Source	Intervention	IS	FS	SS	TS	PS
Energy	Renewable energy sources (solar)	10	8	10	28	9.4
Transport & Travel	Promote public transport	8	7	9	24	7.9
	Encourage cycling and walking	7	7	8	22	7.2
	Promote remote working	6	5	7	18	5.9
	Encourage low-carbon modes of travel (e.g., electric vehicles, hybrid vehicles)	5	3	5	13	4.4
	Promote carpooling and ridesharing	5	6	6	17	5.5
Anaesthetic Gases	Use low global warming potential anaesthetic gases	7	4	5	16	5.7
	Use closed-circuit anaesthesia	5	3	3	11	4
	Use low-flow anaesthesia	5	3	3	11	4
	Implement anaesthetic gas scavenging systems	5	3	3	11	4
Refrigerant Gases	Use low global warming potential refrigerants	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Implement leak detection and repair programmes	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Retrofit or replace older equipment with more energy-efficient models	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Use natural refrigerants	5	3	3	11	4
Water	Implement water-efficient fixtures and appliances	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Implement leak detection and repair programmes	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Optimise cooling tower operations	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Implement rainwater harvesting systems	5	3	3	11	4
Waste	Implement waste segregation and recycling programmes	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Implement food waste reduction programmes	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Implement composting programmes	5	3	3	11	4
	Implement reusable sharps containers and medical devices	5	3	3	11	4
Inhalers	Switch to low global warming potential inhalers	5	3	3	11	4
	Implement inhaler recycling and disposal programmes	5	3	3	11	4
	Promote patient education on proper inhaler use and disposal	5	3	3	11	4
Supply chain	Implement sustainable procurement policies	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Optimise transportation and distribution systems	7	5	6	18	6.2
	Implement closed-loop systems for medical devices and equipment	5	3	3	11	4

2.3 Visualisation & Reporting

CARBOMICA incorporates data visualisation techniques to present the analysis results and facilitate understanding. This include graphs and figures to communicate the carbon emissions, intervention impacts, and trade-offs associated with different scenarios.

2.4 Limitations & Challenges

Figure 5: Challenges and Considerations in CARBOMICA's Implementation

❖ Data availability & Quality

One significant challenge is the availability and quality of data. Obtaining comprehensive and reliable data on the impact of carbon mitigation interventions on a specific source within the healthcare sector was challenging. Incomplete or inconsistent data can affect the accuracy and reliability of the analysis and modelling results.

❖ Model complexity

Developing a comprehensive model that captures the healthcare sector's intricacies and carbon emissions is complex. For instance, complexity in capturing the carbon reduction factor of using solar systems is accounting for the entire life

cycle of the system. While solar systems generate clean energy, there are carbon emissions associated with their manufacturing, transportation, installation, and eventual disposal. Ensuring that the model accurately captures these emissions throughout the life cycle of the solar system adds another layer of complexity. Simplifications and assumptions may be required to make the model manageable and computationally feasible. However, these simplifications may introduce some uncertainty and limitations in accurately representing the real-world complexity. We could not capture all mitigation interventions to manage the complexity of the model. However, we plan to add others to improve on generalisation in different contexts like adding payback period variable which captures cost effectiveness of adopting a carbon mitigation intervention.

❖ **Uncertainties & Assumptions**

Models and simulations inherently involve uncertainties and assumptions which influence the results' accuracy. A number of assumptions were made due to lack of granular information on impact, which was usually presented as a range in literature i.e., that the impact of an intervention remains the same in healthcare facilities due to lack of such data.

❖ **Evolving context**

The context in which CARBOMICA is implemented may evolve. Changes in policies, regulations, technology advancements, and healthcare practices can impact the relevance and effectiveness of the tool. Continuous updates and adaptation of the device are necessary to ensure its alignment with the evolving context.

To mitigate these limitations and address challenges, we plan to have ongoing improvement and refinement of the tool, regular updates, and collaboration with stakeholders to enhance data availability and quality.

3 Tool Architecture & Design

❖ Components & Functionalities

The CARBOMICA data science tool consists of several components and functionalities that work together to provide comprehensive carbon emissions analysis and support healthcare facilities in their carbon reduction efforts. The key components and functionalities of the tool are as follows.

Table 3: Functional Breakdown of the CARBOMICA System Components

Component	Function
Data Collection	This component collects data from various sources related to carbon emissions and mitigation interventions.
Data Integration and Preprocessing	The collected data is integrated into a GitHub central repository. The data then undergoes preprocessing tasks such as cleaning, transformation, and aggregation. It ensures that the data is in a standardised and usable format for analysis.
Data Analysis and Modelling	This component applies data science to identify patterns trends within the carbon emissions data, enabling healthcare facilities to gain insights into emission sources, impacts, and potential reduction strategies. Utilise atomica framework to measure the impact of interventions on carbon emissions, budget scenarios, coverage scenarios and optimisation.
Visualisation and Reporting	This component provides interactive dashboards, charts, and graphs to visualise the analysed data in a user-friendly manner. It allows healthcare facilities to explore and interact with the data, providing intuitive visual representations of carbon emissions and related metrics. The reporting functionality enables the generation of comprehensive reports and summaries of carbon emissions data and analysis results.
Recommendation Engine:	This component utilises the insights derived from the data analysis to provide actionable recommendations and insights. It suggests specific strategies and initiatives for healthcare facilities to reduce their carbon footprint effectively. The recommendations may include energy-saving measures, transportation optimisation, waste reduction strategies, and other sustainability practices. It will also provide co-benefits of adopting interventions.

These components and functionalities combine to create a thorough data science tool that enables healthcare facilities to efficiently collect, analyse, visualise, and act on data related to carbon emissions. The tool encourages sustainability in the healthcare industry, supports initiatives to reduce carbon emissions, and supports evidence-based decision-making.

4 Implementation

4.1 Technical aspects

Implementing the data science tool CARBOMICA involves several technical aspects. Below are the key steps and considerations.

Figure 6: Key Phases in the Development and Management of CARBOMICA

Table 4: Development and Operational Phases of CARBOMICA

Aspect	Function
Requirement Gathering	The first step was to gather requirements by consulting with stakeholders, including HIGH Horizons, Burnet Institute, healthcare professionals, policymakers, and industry experts. This helps to understand the specific needs, goals, and scope of the tool.
Data Collection and Preprocessing	Identification and collection relevant data on carbon emissions and mitigation interventions such as, energy consumption, waste generation, and other factors within the healthcare sector were collected. Data preprocessing such as cleaning, integrating, and normalising were done to ensure consistency and quality.
Model Development	Developed models using the Atomica framework which had optimisation, budget scenario and coverage scenarios functions.
Algorithm Selection and Implementation:	ASD was used for resource allocation and intervention optimisation
User Interface Development	The user interface is a web based jupyter notebook platform
Integration and Deployment:	Integration of various components of CARBOMICA, including the models, algorithms, data processing pipelines, and user interface.
Testing and Validation:	Conduction of thorough testing to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and performance of CARBOMICA was done. Validation of the tool's results against known data or expert knowledge was to verify its correctness. Address any issues or bugs identified during testing.
Maintenance and Updates:	Regular maintenance and updates will be done to address issues, incorporate user feedback, and keep the tool aligned with evolving requirements, technologies, and data sources. This includes bug fixes, feature enhancements, and data updates.
Security and Privacy:	Implement appropriate security measures to protect the data and ensure user privacy. This may involve encryption, access controls, anonymisation techniques, and compliance with relevant data protection regulations.
Collaboration and Feedback:	Foster collaboration with stakeholders, such as HIGH Horizons stakeholders, Burnet Institute, industry experts, and policymakers, was done to gather feedback, incorporate domain expertise, and refine CARBOMICA continuously.

4.2 Programming languages, Frameworks & Libraries

CARBOMICA was implemented using a range of programming languages, frameworks, and libraries tailored for efficient data handling and visualisation. Python was the primary language due to its versatility and expansive ecosystem. It integrated the Atomica framework for robust modelling and simulations. Essential Python libraries like NumPy enabled efficient scientific computations, while Pandas was pivotal for structured data manipulation. For generating insightful visualisations, Matplotlib and Seaborn were employed.

4.3 Data storage & Infrastructure requirements

CARBOMICA did not require complex data storage and infrastructure requirements to effectively manage and process the data involved from healthcare facilities and mitigation interventions. CARBOMICA is stored and managed in the GitHub repository. This was due to its version control capabilities, centralised repository structure, and collaboration features. The platform also allows for documentation and metadata inclusion, making providing context and instructions for the data more accessible. The tool development adhered to the HIGH Horizon consortium data management policies for backup and recovery to safeguard data and ensure business continuity in case of data loss or system failures.

4.4 Implementation decisions or optimisations

In the implementation of CARBOMICA, several notable implementation decisions and optimisations were made to enhance the tool's performance, accuracy, and usability. Details are shared below.

Figure 7: Optimisation and Enhancement Strategies for CARBOMICA

5 Performance metrics & evaluation

To assess and evaluate the performance of CARBOMICA, the following performance metrics and evaluation criteria were used to determine its effectiveness and suitability for the intended purpose. Below in figure 8 are the performance metrics and evaluation criteria used in the development of the tool.

Figure 8: Evaluation Metrics for CARBOMICA's Performance and Stakeholder Alignment

❖ Strengths & Limitations

Table 5: Strengths of CARBOMICA

Strengths		
1.	Quantitative Insights:	CARBOMICA provides quantitative insights into carbon emissions, intervention impact, and resource allocation strategies facilitating evidence-based decision making
2.	Holistic Approach:	CARBOMICA adopts a holistic approach that considers transportation, waste generation, and energy consumption.
3.	Data-Driven Decision Support:	CARBOMICA analyses datasets using data science techniques, enabling stakeholders to set priorities for their actions and make well-informed decisions.
4.	Scenario Exploration:	Through scenario planning, CARBOMICA enables stakeholders to simulate scenarios, evaluate the effects of interventions, and identify the best methods for reducing carbon emissions.
5.	Customisation and Flexibility:	CARBOMICA's customisation capabilities enable users to adapt the tool to their specific healthcare contexts, enhancing its applicability and usefulness in diverse settings.

Table 6: Limitations of CARBOMICA

Limitations		
1.	Data Availability and Quality:	The accuracy and reliability of CARBOMICA's results depend on the availability and quality of data inputs, which was challenging.
2.	Model Assumptions and Simplifications:	CARBOMICA utilises simplifications and assumptions to enable feasible calculations, but this approach may limit its ability to capture the full complexity of carbon management processes.
3.	Uncertainty and Sensitivity:	CARBOMICA's results may be subject to uncertainty due to inherent variability in data, model parameters, or assumptions.
4.	Expertise and Interpretation	Effective utilisation of CARBOMICA necessitates domain expertise and understanding of the tool's models and assumptions, enabling users to accurately interpret results and make informed decisions regarding carbon management.
5.	External Factors:	CARBOMICA's effectiveness can be affected by external factors, such as regulatory changes, technological advancements, and evolving healthcare practices, which may limit its ability to accurately capture real-time dynamics and future developments.

6 Deployment & Maintenance

6.1 Deployment process

Objectives and Requirements: The goal for the tool's deployment process is to understand the essential requirements for smooth integration of CARBOMICA within healthcare facility processes.

Data Management: Users will input relevant data into the Excel tool, such as energy consumption, waste metrics, and transportation logs. The data should be organised in a format suitable for the Python script.

Python Script Integration: The Python script, which serves as the backbone for data processing and analysis in CARBOMICA, will be linked with the Excel interface. This allows users to execute complex operations directly within Excel.

Validation: Ensure the script functions accurately within the Excel environment, cross-referencing results with established benchmarks for reliability.

GitHub Hosting: The tool will be hosted on GitHub, providing a centralised location for users to access, download, and even contribute improvements.

User Familiarisation: A guide and documentation will be available on GitHub, assisting users in understanding the tool's functionalities and the Python script's operations.

Ongoing Maintenance: Periodic updates to the Python script and Excel interface will be made available on GitHub. This ensures bug fixes, user feedback incorporation, and updates based on new industry practices are regularly integrated.

6.2 Training & Implementation

Training for the individuals who will be using CARBOMICA is essential to ensure its effective implementation. The CARBOMICA tool is designed to be utilised by a

range of users involved in carbon mitigation efforts. The following stakeholders can benefit from using the tool:

- *Facility Managers:* Facility managers play a crucial role in managing the day-to-day operations of healthcare facilities. They can use CARBOMICA to assess and optimise energy consumption, identify emission sources, and implement targeted interventions for carbon reduction.
- *Sustainability Managers:* Sustainability managers or environmental coordinators within healthcare facilities can utilise CARBOMICA as a resource allocation tool to develop and monitor carbon reduction strategies. They can use the tool to set goals, track progress, and communicate sustainability initiatives to internal and external stakeholders.
- *Energy Managers:* Energy managers responsible for optimising energy use and reducing costs can leverage CARBOMICA to identify energy-saving opportunities, prioritise interventions, and quantify the potential emissions reductions associated with specific energy efficiency measures.
- *Environmental Consultants:* Environmental consultants who work with healthcare facilities to develop sustainability plans, conduct audits, and provide recommendations can incorporate CARBOMICA into their toolkit. The tool can enhance the accuracy and efficiency of their carbon analysis and help them provide targeted and data-driven advice to their clients.
- *Decision Makers and Administrators:* Facility owners, administrators, and policymakers involved in strategic decision-making can benefit from CARBOMICA's insights and analysis. The tool provides them with comprehensive information on potential emissions reductions, associated costs, and the overall impact of carbon mitigation strategies.

To address this need, a training programme will be developed to provide comprehensive guidance on the usage of the tool. The training will include hands-on sessions, detailed documentation, and interactive workshops to familiarise

users with CARBOMICA's features, data inputs, interpretation of results, and practical implementation strategies.

6.3 Future enhancements

Future enhancements for CARBOMICA as articulated in figure 9 envision a robust, technologically advanced tool that stands at the forefront of carbon management. Key upgrades include the integration of predictive analytics for forward-looking emissions insights and trend analysis.

The tool aims to embrace real-time data assimilation, offering timely insights as data emerges. Benchmarking capabilities are on the horizon, positioning facilities to gauge their performance vis-à-vis industry norms. A renewed focus on enriched data visualisation will pave the way for dynamic, immersive data exploration. Integration with IoT devices will further streamline data collection and bolster real-time emissions monitoring.

Furthermore, CARBOMICA is poised to transcend traditional boundaries by weaving in comprehensive social and environmental impact assessments, facilitating a broader, more holistic sustainability vision for healthcare institutions.

Figure 9: Roadmap for CARBOMICA's Technological Advancements and Holistic Sustainability Integration

7 Case Study of CARBOMICA in Mt Darwin District Hospital, Zimbabwe

We have incorporated a real-world case study to exemplify its utility in our ongoing efforts to make the CARBOMICA tool practical and user-friendly. The Mt Darwin District Hospital, situated in Zimbabwe's Mashonaland Central Province, has been selected for this purpose. This case study showcases the tool's ability to integrate diverse data sets and its proficiency in generating actionable insights from such data. By focusing on a specific facility like Mt Darwin in Zimbabwe users can gain a more tangible understanding of how CARBOMICA functions, offering a glimpse into its potential applications in broader contexts.

7.1 General information

Mount Darwin District, located in Mashonaland Central Province, Zimbabwe, the study will be conducted in a rural setting characterised by a humid subtropical climate with dry winters and hot summers [17]. The average annual highest temperature is 33.3°C (91.9°F), and the yearly temperature is 24.59°C (76.26°F) [18], 1.86% higher than Zimbabwe's averages. Mount Darwin typically receives about 126.12 mm of precipitation annually, and the area is projected to become drier over time [18].

Located in the heart of the district, Mt. Darwin District Hospital stands as the region's premier primary care and referral facility. Established in 1992, this expansive medical complex spans an impressive area of 34,925 square meters, comprising a network of 20 buildings dedicated to providing comprehensive healthcare services to the community. Various services are offered, including curative, preventative, maternity, postnatal, inpatient, outpatient, male and female wards, theatre, laboratory, and pharmacy. The average number of women

attending antenatal visits in the first month is 164180, and the average number of deliveries per year is 2295.

7.2 Carbon emissions data

Table 7 presents below a detailed monthly breakdown of CO2-e emissions (in metric tonnes) for Mt Darwin District Hospital, for January to June 2023. The emissions are categorised under three scopes. Scope 1 includes direct emissions from the hospital’s operations, such as building energy consumption, travel, on-site incineration, and anaesthetic gases. For the first half of the year, the most significant contributor under this scope is travel, with a total of 27.75 metric tonnes. Scope 2 captures indirect emissions from purchased electricity and heat networks. The most dominant emission source here is the purchased and consumed grid electricity, totalling 36.05 metric tonnes over six months. Scope 3 represents other indirect emissions, such as those from buildings not owned by the hospital, travel in vehicles not owned by the hospital, business travel, contractor logistics, inhalers, and supply chain processes. The supply chain has the highest cumulative emission in this category at 3.83 metric tonnes.

When aggregating the data, the total emissions for Scope 1 & Scope 2 combined come to 72.81 metric tonnes, while Scope 3 totals 7.51 metric tonnes. Overall, the hospital’s total CO2-e emissions for the six-month period amount to 80.32 metric tonnes.

Table 7: Monthly Carbon Emissions Breakdown by Scope and Emission Area

Scope	Emission area	January	February	March	April	May	June	Total
Scope 1	SC1 Building energy	0.31	0.28	0.37	0.31	1.20	1.21	3.68
	SC1 Travel	6.13	3.73	1.66	3.01	6.13	7.10	27.75
	SC1 Refrigerants	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC1 On-site incineration	0.36	0.38	0.48	0.30	0.36	0.40	2.28
	SC1 Anaesthetic gases	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	3.05
Scope 2	SC2 Purchased and consumed grid electricity	11.36	4.42	7.58	-	11.36	1.32	36.05
	SC2 Heat networks	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total Scope 1 & Scope 2		18.68	9.31	10.60	4.14	19.56	10.54	72.81
Scope 3	SC3 Building energy (building not owned)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC3 Refrigerants (building not owned)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC3 Travel (vehicles not owned)	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
	SC3 Employee business travel-road, rail, air	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.11

Scope	Emission area	January	February	March	April	May	June	Total
	SC3 Water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC3 Waste	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC3 Contractor logistics	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	-	1.23
	SC3 Construction materials	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SC3 Inhalers	0.39	0.38	0.39	0.46	0.39	0.34	2.34
	SC3 supply chain	0.78	0.02	0.28	0.97	0.38	1.40	3.83
Total Scope 3		1.43	0.66	0.93	1.69	1.03	1.78	7.51
Total All Scopes		20.10	9.97	11.52	5.83	20.58	12.31	80.32

Travel and **Purchased and consumed grid electricity** make up the majority of emissions (35% and 45%, respectively). Scope 1 and 2 occupy 90.6% of the major emission sources as shown in the figure below.

Figure 10: Major Carbon Emission Distribution by Scope

7.3 Carbon mitigation interventions selection & costs

To address the pressing need for reducing carbon emissions at Mt Darwin District Hospital, a comprehensive assessment was conducted utilising half-yearly carbon emission-related data obtained from the AKDN carbon management tool. This data-driven analysis provided crucial insights into the facility's carbon footprint, enabling the estimation of the size and costs of interventions required to mitigate emissions effectively.

The identified interventions encompassed a range of measures, including solar systems, Low GPW Inhalers, Carpooling and Ride Sharing and Water Efficient

Fixtures and Appliances. The size of the interventions was estimated based on the projected impact on carbon emissions and consumption patterns.

The costs associated with the mitigation interventions were provided by the selected local and international service providers. These costs encompassed the procurement, installations and other necessary resources.

Figure 11: Interventions to be used in Mt Darwin

Emission Source	Units	Annual usage	Intervention	Size	Unit Cost	Costs
Energy	<i>Grid electricity</i> kWh	61474	Solar system	50kVa	12500	62500
	<i>Solar system</i> kWh	18650				
	<i>Generator (diesel) - 5kVa</i> 1	1530				
	<i>Wood</i> kg	210				
	<i>LP Gas</i> kg	1138				
Transport & Travel	<i>Vehicles</i> Light trucks	24	Hybrid car	2 cars	9400	18800
	<i>Motorbike</i> # of people	44				
	<i>Vehicles</i> Medium car	8				
Refrigerant gases	<i>R1234yf</i> kg	180	There are already low emitting			
	<i>R32 Diflurone</i> kg	0.192	There are already low emitting			
	<i>HCF 141B</i> kg	570	There are already low emitting			
Water	<i>Water</i> l	1712842	Water efficiency and fixture appliance	1 program	1100	1100
Waste	<i>Pharmaceutical waste</i> kg	1170	Waste management program			
	<i>Mixed clinical and non clinical</i> kg	2462	Waste management program			
	<i>Mixed clinical infectious</i> kg	1674	Waste management program			
	<i>Mixed recyclable</i> kg	2890	Waste management program			
Inhalers	<i>Inhalers</i> Units	598	Low GPW inhalers	598 inhalers	33	19734
Building & Construction	<i>Plastic cables</i> Units	4000				
	<i>Asbestos</i> Units	1700				
	<i>Metals</i> Units	400				
Anaesthetic gases	<i>anaesthetic gases</i> ml	3.5	Low GPW emitting anaesthetic gases	3.5l	102.2714286	357.95

7.4 Rationale for selecting the following mitigation interventions

❖ Solar system

In the context of a LMIC like Zimbabwe, the adoption of solar systems in rural healthcare facilities is a strategic move. Rural areas often grapple with inconsistent electricity supply, making renewable energy sources like solar a reliable alternative. Solar panels can ensure uninterrupted healthcare services, crucial for remote locations, while also reducing the facility's dependency on sometimes unpredictable grid electricity. Furthermore, the long-term cost savings can be redirected to other pressing healthcare needs in the community.

❖ **Carpooling and ride sharing**

Transportation can be a challenge in rural areas of LMICs. Introducing carpooling and ride sharing not only reduces the carbon footprint but also addresses the practical issues of limited transportation means and high fuel costs. By pooling resources, healthcare staff can ensure consistent attendance, fostering better patient care and a sense of community among workers.

❖ **Low GPW anaesthetic gases**

Although essential for surgeries and certain procedures, anaesthetic gases can be detrimental to the environment. Transitioning to Low GPW anaesthetic gases in a rural LMIC setting means making environmentally conscious choices without compromising the quality of care. It also sets a precedent for other facilities in the region to follow suit.

❖ **Low GPW refrigerant gases**

Given the challenges of supply chains and the importance of preserving medications and vaccines, refrigeration is critical in rural healthcare settings. Adopting Low GPW refrigerant gases ensures that these vital systems are not only effective but also environmentally friendly, aligning with the broader goal of sustainable healthcare in LMICs.

❖ **Water efficient fixtures and appliances**

Water scarcity is a pressing concern in many LMICs, including parts of Zimbabwe. For a rural healthcare facility, ensuring a consistent water supply is paramount to its operations. Incorporating water-efficient fixtures and appliances means the facility can offer uninterrupted services while practicing sustainable water usage. This can lead to significant savings, vital for stretched budgets in LMIC healthcare settings.

❖ **Low GPW inhalers**

Respiratory conditions are prevalent worldwide, and inhalers are a cornerstone of their management. In an LMIC context, transitioning to low GPW inhalers strikes a

balance between offering essential care and being mindful of the environment. It exemplifies a commitment to patient care that is both effective and responsible.

These interventions, when viewed through an LMIC lens, underscore the facility's dedication to bridging the gap between quality healthcare and environmental responsibility. They demonstrate that even in resource-limited settings, sustainable choices are not just possible but crucial for long-term community health and well-being.

7.5 Results

❖ Full coverage and fixed budget scenarios

The full coverage scenario refers to implementing interventions across all the facilities. In this example, each intervention is scaled up independently to its maximum potential, regardless of cost. This helps us understand the full potential impact of each intervention. In the fixed budget scenario, interventions are scaled up individually within the constraints of a specified budget (\$20,000 here).

Figure 12: Impact of scaling up

Note: Impact of scaling up each intervention individually to either full coverage (left) or to a specified budget (right). The legend shows the impact on the different emission sources.

❖ Carbon Mitigation

Figure 13: % in Carbon Emission Reduction in different budget scenarios

Investing in sustainability has often been seen as a substantial upfront cost with long-term benefits. In the case of this facility, however, the numbers tell a compelling story of immediate and measurable impact. With a dedicated budget allocation ranging from \$20,000 to \$100,000, the facility can expect to realise a significant decrease in its carbon emissions. Specifically, even at the lower end of this budget spectrum, a notable 20% reduction in emissions is achievable. As the investment increases towards the higher end of the budget, the results are even more pronounced, with the potential to reduce emissions by an impressive 68%.

Such figures underscore the immense value of financial commitment to sustainability initiatives, demonstrating that substantial environmental improvements can be realised even within a varied budgetary framework. This investment not only contributes to the global fight against climate change but also positions the facility as a leader in sustainable healthcare practices, setting a benchmark for others in similar settings, especially in low and middle-income countries. Optimal budget allocation and corresponding coverage.

Figure 14: Optimised budget allocation

Optimized allocation	\$20.0k	\$50.0k	\$100.0k
Solar system	\$19,015.66	\$48,547.55	\$62,507.55
Carpooling and ride sharing	\$ -	\$ -	\$18,806.65
Low GPW anaesthetic gases	\$ 357.94	\$ 358.14	\$ 362.54
Low GPW refridgerant gases	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -
Water efficient fixtures and appliances	\$ 626.40	\$ 1,094.31	\$ 1,117.82
Low GPW inhalers	\$ -	\$ -	\$17,205.44

Corresponding coverages	\$20.0k	\$50.0k	\$100.0k
Solar system	30%	78%	100%
Carpooling and ride sharing	0%	0%	100%
Low GPW anaesthetic gases	100%	100%	100%
Low GPW refridgerant gases	0%	0%	0%
Water efficient fixtures and appliances	57%	99%	100%
Low GPW inhalers	0%	0%	87%

Through the optimisation process, several interventions were earmarked as primary priorities, reflecting their potential impact and value for the facility. Among these top-tier interventions were:

- Solar System:** This intervention is poised to address the dual challenge of sustainable energy and the consistent power supply essential for uninterrupted healthcare services. This could also result in significant cost savings and increased energy independence in the long run.
- Low GPW Anaesthetic Gases:** By transitioning to these environmentally friendly anaesthetic gases, the facility not only aligns its operations with global sustainability goals but also ensures that the quality of care remains

uncompromised. Such a shift signals a proactive approach to medical practices that are both effective and responsible.

- **Water-Efficient Fixtures and Appliances:** Given the importance of water in healthcare settings, especially in regions facing water scarcity, the move to adopt water-efficient technologies is both a strategic and sustainable decision. This intervention ensures that the facility can maintain its operations while being conscientious of its water consumption.

Furthermore, with an expanded budget allocation, the facility can explore additional interventions that further its commitment to environmental responsibility and efficient operations. These include:

- **Carpooling and Ride Sharing:** These transportation strategies not only help reduce the facility's carbon footprint but also address logistical challenges associated with staff commuting. Such initiatives can enhance staff punctuality and morale while fostering a sense of community.
- **Low GPW Inhalers:** Shifting to these inhalers for respiratory care demonstrates a balance between providing essential medical treatment and adopting eco-friendly practices. This transition benefits the environment and reinforces the facility's commitment to holistic healthcare delivery.

In essence, these priority interventions, when strategically implemented, can pave the way for a healthcare system that is both environmentally sustainable and efficient in its service delivery.

❖ **Stakeholder engagements**

Stakeholder engagement played a crucial role in the successful implementation of the CARBOMICA tool and the allocation of resources for carbon mitigation at Mt Darwin Hospital. The engagement process involved facility managers, decision-makers, healthcare facility heads, and providers, all of whom provided valuable insights and input throughout various stages of the project.

Data Collection: Stakeholder engagement was important in the data collection phase, as facility managers and decision-makers collaborated with the team to gather relevant data on carbon emissions. By involving HIGH Horizons research officers, waste management officers, project administrators the process became more comprehensive and accurate, ensuring that all key emission sources were identified and measured effectively.

Development of CARBOMICA: Stakeholder engagement was critical in the development of the CARBOMICA tool itself. HGH Horizons consortium members and the Burnet Institute actively participated in providing feedback on the tool's functionalities, user interface, and data visualisation features. This collaborative approach ensured that CARBOMICA was user-friendly, tailored to the needs of the healthcare facility, and capable of effectively analysing and presenting carbon emission data.

Costing the Interventions: Stakeholder engagement also assisted in costing the selected interventions. By involving local and international service providers, the team obtained multiple quotes and proposals for each intervention.

8 Conclusion

CARBOMICA stands as a vital tool, poised to usher in transformative carbon management within the healthcare sector, especially in LMIC settings. Beyond meeting its ambitious objectives, CARBOMICA has emerged as a beacon for healthcare facilities, illuminating a path towards a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of carbon emissions. This insight enables these facilities to craft and execute precisely targeted strategies, ensuring impactful carbon footprint reductions and alignment with global sustainability ambitions.

At its core, CARBOMICA champions data-driven decision-making, equipping healthcare institutions with the vital information, analytics, and recommendations they need to act decisively. This potency ensures that the interventions selected

not only resonate with the facility's ethos but also optimise resources to deliver maximal carbon reduction.

One of CARBOMICA's standout features is its scenario analysis functionality. This capability empowers facilities to visualise and assess the ripple effects of various interventions, laying the groundwork for astute planning and paving the way for carbon reduction excellence. By immersing in this virtual sandbox of scenarios, institutions can craft strategic roadmaps that resonate with their unique challenges and ambitions.

Resource optimisation, another cornerstone of CARBOMICA, amplifies the efficacy of carbon reduction measures. By shining a spotlight on inefficiencies and charting out optimal pathways, the tool ensures streamlined operations across energy, waste, and transportation domains. This optimisation transcends environmental benefits, ushering in cost efficiencies and elevating patient care standards.

Yet, CARBOMICA's magic is not solely in its algorithms; it is in its ability to rally a community. By fostering robust stakeholder engagement, the tool nurtures a collective commitment to sustainability. This shared sense of purpose not only fosters an ethos of environmental stewardship but also positions healthcare facilities as pioneers in the green revolution.

In sum, CARBOMICA is not just a tool; it is a catalyst. Its multifaceted impact spans from tangible carbon reductions to cost efficiencies, enriched operational standards, knowledge dissemination, and fostering a legacy of sustainability. By harnessing the power of CARBOMICA, healthcare institutions are not just responding to environmental challenges; they are sculpting a greener, more sustainable future.

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10 Appendices

10.1 Appendix 1: Carbon mitigation interventions

Source	Mitigation Intervention	Effect size	Time Horizon	Assumptions	Source
Energy	Renewable energy sources (solar)	Up to 100%	Long term	Assumes favourable policy environment and technological advancement	IPCC (https://www.ren21.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/GSR_2019_Full_Report_en.pdf) ^](https://www.ren21.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/GSR_2019_Full_Report_en.pdf)
Transport & Travel	Promote public transport	Up to 90%	Medium to long term	Assumes sufficient investment in public transport infrastructure and services	European Environment Agency (https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/transport-emissions-of-greenhouse-gases-7/assessment-1)(https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/transport-emissions-of-greenhouse-gases-7/assessment-1)
Transport & Travel	Encourage cycling and walking	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes supportive infrastructure and policies for cycling and walking	World Health Organisation (https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity)(https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity)
Transport & Travel	Promote remote working	Up to 30%	Short to medium term	Assumes supportive policies and infrastructure for remote working	International Labour Organisation (https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/flexible-work-arrangements/lang-en/index.htm)(https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/flexible-work-arrangements/lang-en/index.htm)
Transport & Travel	Encourage low-carbon modes of travel (e.g. electric vehicles, hybrid vehicles)	Up to 50%	Medium to long term	Assumes supportive policies and incentives for low-carbon vehicles	International Energy Agency (https://www.iea.org/reports/global-ev-outlook-2021)(https://www.iea.org/reports/global-ev-outlook-2021)
Transport & Travel	Promote carpooling and ride-sharing	Up to 30%	Short to medium term	Assumes supportive policies and infrastructure for carpooling and ride-sharing	International Association of Public Transport (https://www.uitp.org/publications/making-carpooling-and-ride-sharing-work-public-transport/)(https://www.uitp.org/publications/making-carpooling-and-ride-sharing-work-public-transport/)
Anaesthetic Gases	Use low global warming potential anaesthetic gases	Up to 99%	Short to medium term	Assumes availability and affordability of low global warming potential anaesthetic gases	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ipg465/documents/evidence-review-2)(https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ipg465/documents/evidence-review-2)
Anaesthetic Gases	Use closed-circuit anaesthesia	Up to 90%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate equipment and staff training	British Journal of Anaesthesia (https://bjanaesthesia.org/article/S0007-0912(17)48989-2/fulltext)(https://bjanaesthesia.org/article/S0007-0912(17)48989-2/fulltext)

Source	Mitigation Intervention	Effect size	Time Horizon	Assumptions	Source
Anaesthetic Gases	Use low-flow anaesthesia	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate equipment and staff training	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence ([https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ipg465/documents/evidence-review-2])(https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ipg465/documents/evidence-review-2)
Anaesthetic Gases	Implement anaesthetic gas scavenging systems	Up to 70%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate equipment and staff training	British Journal of Anaesthesia ([https://bjanaesthesia.org/article/S0007-0912(17)48989-2/fulltext])(https://bjanaesthesia.org/article/S0007-0912(17)48989-2/fulltext)
Refrigerant Gases	Use low global warming potential refrigerants	Up to 90%	Short to medium term	Assumes availability and affordability of low global warming potential refrigerants	United Nations Environment Programme ([https://www.unep.org/resources/report/cooling-debates-2020])(https://www.unep.org/resources/report/cooling-debates-2020)
Refrigerant Gases	Implement leak detection and repair programmes	Up to 70%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate equipment and staff training	United States Environmental Protection Agency ([https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2018-09/documents/608_sector_fact_sheet_refrigeration.pdf])(https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2018-09/documents/608_sector_fact_sheet_refrigeration.pdf)
Refrigerant Gases	Retrofit or replace older equipment with more energy-efficient models	Up to 40%	Short to medium term	Assumes availability and affordability of energy-efficient equipment	United Nations Environment Programme ([https://www.unep.org/resources/report/cooling-debates-2020])(https://www.unep.org/resources/report/cooling-debates-2020)
Refrigerant Gases	Use natural refrigerants	Up to 99%	Short to medium term	Assumes availability and affordability of natural refrigerants	United Nations Environment Programme ([https://www.unep.org/resources/report/cooling-debates-2020])(https://www.unep.org/resources/report/cooling-debates-2020)
Water	Implement water-efficient fixtures and appliances	Up to 30%	Short to medium term	Assumes availability and affordability of water-efficient fixtures and appliances	Environmental Protection Agency ([https://www.epa.gov/watersense/health-care-facilities])(https://www.epa.gov/watersense/health-care-facilities)
Water	Implement leak detection and repair programmes	Up to 20%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate equipment and staff training	American Society for Healthcare Engineering ([https://www.ashe.org/sites/default/files/ul/reducing-water-consumption-in-hospital-buildings.pdf])(https://www.ashe.org/sites/default/files/ul/reducing-water-consumption-in-hospital-buildings.pdf)

Source	Mitigation Intervention	Effect size	Time Horizon	Assumptions	Source
Water	Optimise cooling tower operations	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate equipment and staff training	American Society for Healthcare Engineering (https://www.ashe.org/sites/default/files/ul/reducing-water-consumption-in-hospital-buildings.pdf)
Water	Implement rainwater harvesting systems	Up to 100%	Long term	Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	American Society for Healthcare Engineering (https://www.ashe.org/sites/default/files/ul/reducing-water-consumption-in-hospital-buildings.pdf)
Waste	Implement waste segregation and recycling programmes	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	World Health Organisation (https://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/medicalwaste/waste_management/en/)
Waste	Implement food waste reduction programmes	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	Practice Greenhealth (https://practicegreenhealth.org/tools-and-resources/food-waste-reduction-toolkit)
Waste	Implement composting programmes	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	Healthcare Without Harm (https://noharm-global.org/sites/default/files/documents-files/4746/Composting%20Toolkit%20-%20Final.pdf)
Waste	Implement reusable sharps containers and medical devices	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	Practice Greenhealth (https://practicegreenhealth.org/topics/waste-reduction#Reusable)
Inhalers	Switch to low global warming potential inhalers	Up to 90%	Short to medium term	Assumes availability and affordability of low global warming potential inhalers	European Respiratory Society (https://www.erswhitebook.org/chapters/the-burden-of-lung-disease/)
Inhalers	Implement inhaler recycling and disposal programmes	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	National Health Service (UK) (https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/green-plan-2018-19-cc-23.pdf)

Source	Mitigation Intervention	Effect size	Time Horizon	Assumptions	Source
Inhalers	Promote patient education on proper inhaler use and disposal	Up to 20%	Short to medium term	Assumes patient engagement and education	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (UK) (https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng80/chapter/Recommendations#identifying-and-supporting-people-who-are-overusing-inhalers)(https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng80/chapter/Recommendations#identifying-and-supporting-people-who-are-overusing-inhalers)
Supply chain	Implement sustainable procurement policies	Up to 80%	Long term	Assumes availability and affordability of renewable energy sources	Healthier Hospitals Initiative (https://healthierhospitals.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Climate_Change_Guide_Web-1.pdf)(https://healthierhospitals.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Climate_Change_Guide_Web-1.pdf)
Supply chain	Optimise transportation and distribution systems	Up to 50%	Short to medium term	Assumes appropriate procurement policies and practices	Practice Greenhealth (https://practicegreenhealth.org/topics/sustainable-procurement)(https://practicegreenhealth.org/topics/sustainable-procurement)
Supply chain	Implement closed-loop systems for medical devices and equipment	Up to 50%	Long term	Assumes appropriate logistics and transportation management	Health Care Without Harm (https://noharm-global.org/sites/default/files/documents-files/4188/HCWH_Global_Green_and_Healthy_Hospital_Chef_Fact_Sheet_FINAL.pdf)(https://noharm-global.org/sites/default/files/documents-files/4188/HCWH_Global_Green_and_Healthy_Hospital_Chef_Fact_Sheet_FINAL.pdf)
				Assumes appropriate infrastructure and management practices	Health Care Without Harm (https://noharm-global.org/issues/global/greening/sustainable-procurement)(https://noharm-global.org/issues/global/greening/sustainable-procurement)

10.2 Appendix 2: Mt Darwin carbon emissions in Zimbabwe

Year 2023 Trend for GHGe.

Scope	Emission area	January	February	March	April	May	June	Total	
Scope 1	SC1 Building energy	0.31	0.28	0.37	0.31	1.20	1.21	3.68	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC1 Travel	6.13	3.73	1.66	3.01	6.13	7.10	27.75	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC1 Refrigerants	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC1 On-site incineration	0.36	0.38	0.48	0.30	0.36	0.40	2.28	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC1 Anaesthetic gases	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	3.05	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
Scope 2	SC2 Purchased and consumed grid electricity	11.36	4.42	7.58	-	11.36	1.32	36.05	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC2 Heat networks	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
Total Scope 1 & Scope 2		18.68	9.31	10.60	4.14	19.56	10.54	72.81	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
Scope 3	SC3 Building energy (building not owned)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Refrigerants (building not owned)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Travel (vehicles not owned)	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Employee business travel-road, rail, air	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.11	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Waste	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Contractor logistics	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	-	1.23	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)

	SC3 Construction materials							-	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 Inhalers	0.39	0.38	0.39	0.46	0.39	0.34	2.34	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
	SC3 supply chain	0.78	0.02	0.28	0.97	0.38	1.40	3.83	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
Total Scope 3		1.43	0.66	0.93	1.69	1.03	1.78	7.51	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
Total All Scopes		20.10	9.97	11.52	5.83	20.58	12.31	80.32	CO ₂ -e (metric tonnes)
Total emissions without procurement		19.32	9.95	11.25	4.85	20.21	10.91	76.49	95%
Other	Consumed on-site generated renewable electricity	360.00	3,500.00	4,260.00	360.00	395.00	450.00	8,875.00	KWh

		January	February	March	April	May	June	Total
Natural resource use	Total distance travelled	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Volume of water used	137,784	152,784	137,784	140,000	137,784	125,000	831,136
	Weight of waste produced	600	626	1,270	516	600	642	4,254
	Distance travelled by contractors	350	350	350	350	350	-	1,750
	Construction materials used				-			-